

A Taxonomy for the Use of Quantum Computing in Drone Video Streaming Technology

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Abstract:- With the rapid advancement of drone technology, the demand for high-quality and real-time video streaming from drones has significantly increased. However, existing classical computing techniques face numerous challenges in meeting the requirements of efficient video encoding, transmission, and decoding. Quantum computing has emerged as a promising approach to address these limitations by leveraging quantum algorithms and principles to enhance various aspects of video streaming systems. This paper presents a taxonomy for the use of quantum computing in drone video streaming technology. The taxonomy is designed to categorize and classify the diverse applications of quantum computing in the different stages of drone video streaming, including video compression, encryption, transmission, and decoding. The taxonomy framework encompasses both theoretical and practical aspects, considering the current state of quantum computing technologies and their potential impact on drone video streaming. The taxonomy is structured into several key dimensions, including quantum algorithms, quantum-enhanced data compression techniques, quantum encryption methods, and quantum-assisted transmission and decoding strategies. Each dimension is further divided into subcategories that explore specific approaches and methodologies relevant to quantum computing in drone video streaming. Furthermore, the paper highlights the benefits and challenges associated with the adoption of quantum computing in this domain. It discusses how quantum computing can improve video compression efficiency, enhance data security through quantum encryption algorithms, enable faster and more reliable transmission using quantum-assisted techniques, and facilitate real-time video decoding with the aid of quantum algorithms. Through this taxonomy, researchers and practitioners in the field of drone video streaming can gain a comprehensive understanding of the potential applications and implications of quantum computing. It serves as a valuable reference for exploring innovative solutions and design considerations to harness the power of quantum computing in improving the performance and capabilities of drone video streaming systems.

Keywords:- Quantum Computing, Drone Video Streaming, Taxonomy, Video Compression, Encryption, Transmission, Decoding.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computing [9] is an emerging field that has the potential to revolutionize various industries, including drone technology. While quantum computing is not yet extensively integrated into drones, researchers are exploring its potential applications. We now discuss a few ways quantum computing could be used in drone technology. Drones often face complex optimization problems, such as finding the most efficient path for navigation, scheduling tasks, or optimizing resource allocation. Quantum computing's ability to handle large-scale optimization problems and search algorithms could potentially enhance the efficiency of path planning for drones, leading to optimized routes and improved resource allocation.

Quantum computing's computational power can aid in complex weather modeling and analysis. Drones equipped with quantum computers could leverage this capability to make real-time weather predictions, enabling them to navigate more safely and efficiently. It could also assist in analyzing weather patterns for applications like precision agriculture, disaster management, and aerial surveillance. In addition, quantum computing algorithms may enhance the capabilities of drones in image processing and object recognition tasks. Quantum image processing algorithms could help drones process and analyze visual data more quickly and accurately, enabling them to identify objects, detect anomalies, and respond accordingly. Also, drones typically rely on multiple sensors to gather data about their surroundings. Quantum computing algorithms can assist in fusing data from various sensors, including cameras, LiDAR [19], and radar, to create a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of the environment. This fusion of sensor data could improve situational awareness and decision-making capabilities for drones. Furthermore, quantum computing is known for its potential in cryptography. As drones often require secure communication and data transmission, quantum encryption techniques could provide an extra layer of security. Quantum key distribution (QKD) protocols could enable secure communication channels between drones, ground stations, and other devices, protecting sensitive information from potential eavesdropping.

Video streaming [14] plays a crucial role in drone technology, allowing operators to view live video feeds from the drone's camera in real-time. We now discuss some key aspects related to video streaming in drone technology. Drones are equipped with cameras that capture video footage during flight. These cameras can vary in terms of resolution, frame rate, field of view, and other specifications, depending

on the drone's purpose and capabilities. Additionally, to efficiently transmit video data from the drone to the ground station or other receiving devices, video compression techniques are employed. Commonly used compression algorithms include H.264 (AVC), H.265 (HEVC), and VP9 [18], which reduce the size of the video data while maintaining an acceptable level of quality. Also, drones typically utilize wireless communication technologies to transmit video data to the ground station or remote devices. This can involve using Wi-Fi, radio frequency (RF), or other wireless protocols depending on the drone's specifications. The choice of communication technology impacts the range, bandwidth, and latency of the video streaming.

Furthermore, the video stream from the drone is received and displayed on a ground station or remote devices, such as smartphones, tablets, or dedicated monitors. These devices provide a real-time view of the drone's perspective, enabling operators to monitor the flight, capture images or videos, and make informed decisions based on the visual data. In addition, ensuring a high-quality video streaming experience is essential. Factors such as video resolution, frame rate, latency, and stability are important considerations. Optimizing these parameters, along with maintaining a reliable and consistent video stream, is crucial for effective drone operations. Moreover, bandwidth availability and transmission stability influence the quality of video streaming. Drones must account for potential limitations in bandwidth, especially in remote or congested areas. Intelligent transmission protocols are employed to adapt to varying network conditions, ensuring smooth and uninterrupted video streaming.

In addition to video streaming, drones also transmit telemetry data, including flight parameters, GPS coordinates, battery levels, and other relevant information. This data is crucial for monitoring and controlling the drone's flight, complementing the video stream and enabling efficient operation. Also, protecting the privacy and integrity of the video stream is important, especially in sensitive applications. Encryption techniques, such as Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) or Virtual Private Network (VPN) protocols [6], may be employed to secure the video transmission and prevent unauthorized access or tampering. Video streaming technology in drone applications continues to advance, driven by developments in wireless communication, video compression, and processing capabilities. These advancements aim to provide operators with high-quality, real-time video feeds, enhancing situational awareness, data analysis, and decision-making during drone operations.

This work presents a comprehensive taxonomy for the utilization of quantum computing in drone video streaming technology. With the growing demand for high-quality and real-time video streaming from drones, classical computing approaches face limitations in meeting the requirements of efficient encoding, transmission, and decoding. By categorizing and classifying the applications of quantum computing in various stages of drone video streaming, including compression, encryption, transmission, and decoding, the taxonomy provides researchers and practitioners with a framework to understand and explore the potential

benefits and challenges associated with integrating quantum computing techniques. This taxonomy serves as a valuable resource for advancing the performance and capabilities of drone video streaming systems through quantum computing advancements.

II. VIDEO STREAMING

A. Types of Video Streaming

There are several types of video streaming that cater to different purposes and requirements. We now discuss some common types. Live streaming allows viewers to watch video content in real-time as it is happening. It has gained immense popularity in recent years due to its ability to bring events, conferences, sports matches, and other live content to a global audience. With live streaming, viewers can experience the excitement and immediacy of an event from the comfort of their own devices. It offers real-time interaction and engagement through features like live chat, comments, and social media integration, enabling viewers to connect with each other and with the content creators in a dynamic and interactive manner. Live streaming has revolutionized the way we consume and participate in live events, providing an immersive and inclusive viewing experience regardless of geographical boundaries.

Video-on-Demand (VOD) streaming [24] refers to the ability for users to access a library of pre-recorded video content and stream it at their convenience. VOD platforms offer a wide range of videos, such as movies, TV shows, documentaries, and user-generated content, which users can select and watch whenever they want. Unlike traditional broadcast television, VOD allows viewers to have control over what they watch and when they watch it. Popular VOD platforms like Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, YouTube, and others have transformed the way we consume video content, providing extensive libraries of on-demand content accessible across a variety of devices, from smartphones and tablets to smart TVs and streaming media players. With VOD streaming, users have the flexibility to choose from a vast selection of content and enjoy it at their own pace, making it a highly popular and convenient form of video consumption in the digital age.

Adaptive Bitrate Streaming (ABR) is a streaming technique that dynamically adjusts the quality of a video stream based on the viewer's internet connection speed and device capabilities [14]. The goal of ABR is to provide a smooth viewing experience by adapting the bitrate and resolution of the video in real-time to match the available network bandwidth. ABR works by encoding the video content at multiple bitrates and storing them as different versions or representations [13]. As the video is streamed, the ABR algorithm monitors the viewer's network conditions, such as bandwidth fluctuations and latency, and selects the appropriate representation that can be delivered smoothly without buffering. This adaptive process ensures that the video playback remains uninterrupted and optimized for the viewer's specific environment [16]. If the viewer's internet connection improves, the ABR algorithm can automatically switch to a higher-quality representation, providing a sharper

and more detailed video. Conversely, if the network conditions deteriorate, the ABR algorithm will adapt by selecting a lower-quality representation to prevent buffering and maintain a continuous stream. ABR is widely used in various streaming platforms and services, including video-on-demand (VOD) providers, live streaming events, and over-the-top (OTT) media delivery. It enhances the user experience by delivering the best possible video quality while mitigating issues related to varying network conditions, thereby ensuring a seamless and optimized streaming experience for viewers across different devices [15] and network environments.

Progressive Download [8] is a streaming method that enables viewers to start watching a video while it is still being downloaded to their device. In this approach, the video file is delivered in a way that allows playback to begin before the complete file has finished downloading. When a viewer initiates the playback of a video using progressive download, the video file is fetched from a server and saved to a temporary storage location on the viewer's device. As the file downloads, the video player starts playing the portion that has been downloaded, allowing the viewer to watch the video in real-time. This approach eliminates the need to wait for the entire video file to be downloaded before playback can begin, resulting in a quicker start time and a smoother viewing experience. Progressive download is commonly used for smaller video files or in situations where streaming infrastructure, such as a dedicated streaming server or adaptive streaming protocols, may not be available or required. It is often utilized for online video playback on websites or platforms where the video file can be directly accessed and downloaded by the viewer. However, it's important to note that progressive download does not offer the same benefits as true streaming methods like adaptive bitrate streaming (ABR) when it comes to dynamically adjusting the video quality based on the viewer's internet connection speed. Progressive download simply allows playback to start before the entire file is downloaded, providing a perceived faster start time for viewers.

Peer-to-Peer (P2P) streaming [28] is a streaming method that harnesses the combined bandwidth and resources of multiple viewers to distribute video content. In traditional streaming, a central server delivers the content to each viewer individually, which can create high server load and network congestion, especially for popular or bandwidth-intensive videos. P2P streaming alleviates this strain by enabling viewers to share the distribution responsibility amongst themselves. In P2P streaming, when a viewer requests a video, the streaming application connects them to a network of peers who are also streaming or have already downloaded the same content. Instead of relying solely on the central server, the viewer receives different parts of the video from multiple peers, who act as both sources and receivers of the content. As the viewer streams the video, they simultaneously upload the parts they have already received to other viewers who are requesting the same content. This collaborative sharing approach distributes the load across multiple peers and reduces the dependence on a single server for content delivery. P2P streaming offers several advantages. First, it can significantly reduce the strain on the central server, as the

workload is distributed among the viewers. Second, it enables efficient content delivery, especially for popular videos, as more peers become available to share the content. Additionally, P2P streaming can enhance the scalability and reliability of video distribution, as the network can adapt to fluctuations in viewer demand and handle failures by dynamically finding alternative sources for the missing or unavailable video segments. However, it's important to note that P2P streaming may introduce challenges related to content availability, network security, and privacy, as viewers rely on each other for content delivery. Proper protocols and mechanisms need to be implemented to ensure the integrity and authenticity of the content being shared and to protect the privacy of the viewers involved in the P2P network. Overall, P2P streaming leverages the collective resources of viewers to create a distributed and efficient content delivery system, reducing the strain on central servers and enabling scalable and reliable video streaming.

Secure streaming [3] refers to the implementation of encryption and digital rights management (DRM) technologies to safeguard copyrighted content and prevent unauthorized access, copying, or piracy. Encryption plays a crucial role in secure streaming by encoding the video content in a manner that can only be decoded and viewed by authorized parties. Encryption algorithms scramble the video data, making it unreadable without the appropriate decryption keys. This ensures that even if the video stream is intercepted or obtained by unauthorized individuals, they would not be able to access the original content. DRM technologies complement encryption by managing and enforcing the usage rights associated with the video content. DRM systems control how the content is accessed, copied, distributed, and protected against unauthorized actions. They typically employ techniques such as license management, access controls, watermarking, and digital signatures to ensure that only authorized viewers or devices can decrypt and play the protected content. Secure streaming systems integrate encryption and DRM technologies to provide a robust and comprehensive approach to protect copyrighted video content. This is particularly important for streaming platforms that offer premium or subscription-based services, where content owners and distributors need assurance that their intellectual property is safeguarded against piracy and unauthorized redistribution. By implementing secure streaming techniques, content providers can confidently deliver their video content to viewers, knowing that it is protected from unauthorized access, piracy, and illegal distribution. It helps preserve the integrity of the content and ensures that content creators and distributors are appropriately compensated for their work. It's worth noting that secure streaming does not only benefit copyright holders but also contributes to maintaining viewer trust and fostering a sustainable digital media ecosystem where content creators can continue to produce high-quality video content.

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) streaming [23] techniques are specifically tailored to deliver immersive experiences by streaming 360-degree videos for VR or overlaying digital content onto the real world for AR. These forms of streaming require specialized formats and

technologies to cater to the unique demands of VR and AR content. VR streaming involves capturing video footage from multiple perspectives to create a 360-degree view of the environment. Viewers wearing VR headsets can then immerse themselves in the video and explore the virtual world as if they were physically present. Streaming such content requires encoding and delivery formats that maintain the high resolution and fidelity needed for an immersive experience. AR streaming, on the other hand, involves overlaying virtual objects or information onto the real-world environment. This can include placing virtual objects in a live video stream or enhancing live video with contextual information. AR streaming requires the real-time synchronization of the virtual content with the real-world video feed, enabling viewers to interact with the digital elements seamlessly. Both VR and AR streaming demand specialized codecs, delivery protocols, and adaptive streaming techniques to ensure low latency, high-quality playback, and smooth interactivity. Additionally, these streaming methods require robust bandwidth and network capabilities due to the large amount of data involved in rendering immersive VR or AR experiences. VR and AR streaming technologies are advancing rapidly to meet the growing demand for immersive content. They have applications in gaming, entertainment, education, training, and various industries that leverage the power of immersive experiences. As these technologies continue to evolve, streaming platforms and content providers are focusing on optimizing the delivery and quality of VR and AR content, ultimately enhancing the overall user experience in these immersive environments. These are just a few examples of the types of video streaming methods available. Depending on the specific requirements, context, and technological advancements, new types of streaming may continue to emerge.

B. Video Streaming in Drones

Among the types of video streaming listed, the most commonly used streaming type in drones is live streaming. Drones are often equipped with cameras that capture real-time video footage, which can be transmitted and streamed in real-time to viewers or operators. Live streaming allows viewers to experience the drone's perspective and observe events or locations as they happen, enabling various applications such as aerial photography, surveillance, and live reporting. Other streaming types listed, such as Video-on-Demand (VOD), Adaptive Bitrate Streaming (ABR), Progressive Download, Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Streaming, Secure Streaming, and Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) Streaming, may have applications in drones depending on specific use cases, but live streaming is the most prevalent and widely used in drone video streaming technology.

Live streaming is particularly relevant for drones as it allows real-time broadcasting of video content captured by the drone's camera. This enables viewers to watch the drone's perspective and experience events or locations in real-time as the drone is flying. Live streaming from drones is often utilized for various applications such as aerial photography, surveillance, sports events, and live reporting. On the other hand, VOD streaming is also employed in drones, especially for scenarios where recorded video footage needs to be stored

and later accessed by users. For example, in surveying, inspection, or research applications, drones may capture high-quality video footage that is later processed, analyzed, or reviewed by experts or stakeholders. VOD streaming enables efficient access to this recorded video content, allowing users to retrieve specific portions of the footage and review it at their convenience. Both live streaming and VOD streaming can be implemented in drone video streaming technology, depending on the specific use case, requirements, and constraints of the application at hand.

III. DRONE TECHNOLOGY

Drone technology [26], also known as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), refers to the use of remotely controlled or autonomous aircraft systems that can fly without a human pilot on board. Drones have gained significant popularity and have seen advancements in recent years due to their wide range of applications in various industries. We now describe the basic components of a drone. The first component is the frame which is the physical structure that houses all the internal components and provides stability and maneuverability. The second component is the motors and propellers which consists of electric motors and propellers provide the necessary thrust to lift and move the drone in different directions. The third component is the flight controller. The flight controller is the brain of the drone, consisting of sensors, microprocessors, and software algorithms that manage and stabilize the flight by adjusting the motors' speed and direction. The fourth component is the GPS and navigation system. Drones often feature GPS receivers and navigation systems that enable autonomous flight, precise positioning, and waypoint navigation. The fifth component is the onboard sensors. Drones can be equipped with various sensors, such as accelerometers, gyroscopes, altimeters, compasses, and obstacle avoidance sensors. These sensors provide crucial data for flight stabilization, altitude control, orientation, and collision avoidance. The sixth component is the camera and gimbal. Many drones are equipped with cameras or payload systems to capture photos, videos, or collect data. Some advanced drones include gimbals, which are mechanical stabilizers that ensure smooth and stabilized footage. The seventh component is the transmitter and receiver. Drones use a wireless communication system consisting of a transmitter (remote controller) operated by the pilot and a receiver on the drone that receives the control signals. The eighth component is the batteries. Drones are powered by rechargeable batteries, typically lithium-ion or lithium polymer batteries, which provide the necessary electrical energy for flight.

Drones have a wide range of applications across various industries. We now discuss some of them. The first is in Aerial Photography and Videography. Drones equipped with high-quality cameras provide stunning aerial imagery and videos for photography, filmmaking, real estate, and surveying. The second is in Delivery Services. Companies are exploring the use of drones for package delivery in areas with challenging terrain or remote locations. The third is in Agriculture. Drones can be used for crop monitoring, aerial spraying, and precision agriculture, enabling farmers to

monitor plant health, optimize irrigation, and improve crop yields. The fourth is in Inspection and Maintenance. Drones equipped with cameras or specialized sensors can inspect infrastructure, such as power lines, pipelines, and buildings, for maintenance and safety purposes. The fifth is in Search and Rescue. Drones equipped with thermal cameras and GPS capabilities assist in search and rescue operations, locating missing individuals or providing aerial support in emergency situations. The sixth is in Mapping and Surveying. Drones equipped with GPS and cameras can capture aerial imagery and generate high-resolution maps, 3D models, and topographic data for surveying, urban planning, and environmental monitoring. The seventh is in Entertainment and Racing. Drones are used in recreational activities, including drone racing events, aerial acrobatics, and drone light shows. As drone technology continues to advance, new features and capabilities are being introduced, including obstacle avoidance systems, improved flight stability, longer flight times, autonomous flight modes, and integration with artificial intelligence and computer vision technologies. However, it's important to note that drone usage is regulated by aviation authorities in different countries to ensure safety, privacy, and compliance with local regulations.

Video streaming applications in drones involve the real-time transmission of video footage captured by the drone's onboard camera to remote viewers or operators. These applications leverage the capabilities of drones to provide live video feeds, enabling various use cases and industries to benefit from aerial perspectives and real-time situational awareness. We now describe video streaming applications in drones. The first is in Aerial Photography and Videography [31]. Drones equipped with high-quality cameras stream live video feeds, allowing photographers and filmmakers to monitor the composition, framing, and quality of their shots in real-time. This application is widely used in film production, cinematography, and professional photography. The second is in Surveillance and Security [4]. Drones with cameras can stream live video feeds for surveillance purposes. They provide a bird's-eye view, enabling security personnel to monitor large areas, public events, or critical infrastructure in real-time. Live streaming enhances situational awareness and can aid in detecting and responding to security threats promptly. The third is in Search and Rescue Operations [22]. Drones equipped with cameras and thermal imaging sensors can stream live video feeds during search and rescue missions. These drones can cover large areas quickly, provide real-time video feedback to search teams, and assist in locating missing individuals or identifying hazards. The fourth is in Inspection and Monitoring [10]. Drones can stream live video feeds during inspections of infrastructure, such as power lines, pipelines, bridges, or buildings. This application allows inspectors to remotely monitor the condition of structures, detect faults or damages, and plan necessary maintenance or repairs more efficiently. The fifth is in Emergency Response [2]. Drones with live video streaming capabilities can provide valuable situational awareness during emergency response operations. They can assess the extent of damage, aid in coordination efforts, and provide crucial real-time information to emergency responders. The sixth is in Real Estate and Property Marketing [20]. Drones streaming live video feeds

offer a unique perspective for showcasing properties, land, or real estate developments. Potential buyers or investors can remotely view properties in real-time, enhancing the marketing and sales process. The seventh is in Sports Events and Broadcasting [21]. Drones with cameras can stream live video feeds of sporting events, enabling viewers to experience the action from unique angles and perspectives. This application enhances sports broadcasting and provides immersive viewing experiences. The eighth is in Environmental Monitoring [32]. Drones streaming live video can be used for environmental monitoring and research purposes. They can capture aerial views of landscapes, wildlife, or ecological phenomena, providing real-time data for scientific studies and environmental management. These are just a few examples of video streaming applications in drones. As drone technology continues to advance, live video streaming capabilities become increasingly accessible, opening up more opportunities for industries to leverage the aerial perspective and real-time video feeds provided by drones.

IV. TAXONOMY

Here is a taxonomy outlining potential use cases of quantum computing in drone video streaming technology.

A. Video Compression and Encoding

- *Quantum-Based Video Compression [11]: Quantum computing algorithms could be utilized to improve video compression techniques, enabling more efficient encoding and reducing bandwidth requirements for streaming high-quality video from drones.*

Quantum-based video compression is an emerging area of research that explores the potential of quantum computing algorithms to enhance traditional video compression techniques. Video compression is crucial for efficient storage and transmission of video content, and advancements in this field can have significant implications for streaming high-quality video from drones. Quantum computing algorithms offer the possibility of solving certain computational problems more efficiently than classical algorithms. In the context of video compression, quantum algorithms could potentially improve the efficiency of encoding and decoding processes, leading to more compact representations of video data. By leveraging quantum computing techniques, it may be possible to develop new compression algorithms that can achieve higher compression ratios without sacrificing video quality. These algorithms could exploit quantum properties such as superposition and entanglement to extract more information from the video data and represent it in a more concise manner. Reducing the bandwidth requirements for video streaming from drones is particularly important as it enables real-time transmission of high-quality video footage without significant delays or network congestion. Efficient video compression techniques based on quantum computing could contribute to reducing the amount of data that needs to be transmitted, optimizing bandwidth utilization, and enhancing the overall streaming experience. However, it's important to note that quantum-based video compression is still in its early stages, and practical implementations are yet to be fully realized.

Quantum computers with sufficient power and stability for complex video compression tasks are still under development. Additionally, quantum algorithms need to be further researched, optimized, and tested in real-world scenarios to evaluate their effectiveness in video compression applications. Nonetheless, the potential of quantum-based video compression offers exciting prospects for the future of drone video streaming and other video-related applications. As quantum computing technology continues to progress, it may unlock new possibilities for more efficient video encoding and compression, ultimately enhancing the streaming capabilities of drones and improving the overall efficiency and quality of video transmission.

- *Quantum Image Processing [12]: Quantum algorithms can enhance image processing tasks involved in video compression, leading to improved video quality and reduced data size for streaming.*

Quantum image processing is a rapidly evolving field that explores the potential of quantum computing algorithms to enhance various image processing tasks, including those involved in video compression. By leveraging the unique properties of quantum computing, quantum algorithms have the potential to improve video quality and reduce the data size required for streaming. Image processing tasks in video compression involve operations such as image enhancement, noise reduction, color correction, and spatial and temporal compression. Quantum algorithms can potentially offer advantages over classical algorithms in terms of computational efficiency and optimization. One area where quantum algorithms can have an impact is in the optimization of image compression techniques. Quantum algorithms can potentially provide more effective methods for quantization, which is a critical step in compressing images and videos. By leveraging the quantum properties of superposition and entanglement, quantum algorithms can explore larger solution spaces and potentially find more optimal representations of image data. Additionally, quantum algorithms can enhance other image processing tasks that are integral to video compression, such as denoising and interpolation. These tasks aim to improve the visual quality of videos by reducing noise and filling in missing or interpolated frames. Quantum algorithms could potentially provide more efficient and accurate methods for these operations, resulting in higher-quality videos with reduced data size. However, it's important to note that quantum image processing is still an area of active research, and practical implementations are yet to be fully realized. Quantum computers with sufficient power and stability for complex image processing tasks are still being developed, and quantum algorithms need further refinement and testing in real-world scenarios. Nonetheless, the potential of quantum image processing in enhancing video compression and improving streaming quality is promising. As quantum computing technology advances, it may unlock new possibilities for more efficient and effective image processing techniques, ultimately leading to improved video quality and reduced data size for streaming from drones and other video streaming applications.

B. Real-Time Video Analytics

- *Quantum Object Detection and Tracking [27]: Quantum computing algorithms can be applied to real-time object detection and tracking in drone video streams, enabling advanced analytics and identification of objects of interest.*

Quantum object detection and tracking is an emerging area of research that explores the potential of quantum computing algorithms to enhance real-time object detection and tracking tasks in drone video streams. By leveraging the unique properties of quantum computing, these algorithms aim to improve the accuracy and efficiency of object identification and tracking in drone video footage. Object detection and tracking in drone video streams involve the identification and localization of specific objects or targets of interest within the video frames and then tracking their movements across successive frames. This task is crucial for various applications, including surveillance, search and rescue, autonomous navigation, and monitoring. Quantum computing algorithms offer the potential for more efficient and powerful processing of large datasets involved in object detection and tracking. Quantum algorithms can leverage quantum parallelism and superposition to perform computations on multiple possibilities simultaneously, potentially reducing the computational complexity of object detection algorithms and enabling faster processing of video frames. Furthermore, quantum algorithms can provide enhanced feature extraction capabilities, allowing for more accurate object representation and recognition. By leveraging quantum machine learning techniques, these algorithms can learn complex patterns and relationships within the video data, enabling improved object identification and tracking even in challenging scenarios such as occlusions, cluttered backgrounds, or low-light conditions. However, it's important to note that quantum object detection and tracking is still in its early stages, and practical implementations are yet to be fully realized. Quantum computers with sufficient power and stability for complex real-time video processing tasks are still under development. Additionally, quantum algorithms need further research, optimization, and testing to evaluate their effectiveness and robustness in real-world drone video streaming applications. Nonetheless, the potential of quantum object detection and tracking offers exciting prospects for advanced analytics and identification of objects of interest in drone video streams. As quantum computing technology continues to advance, it may unlock new possibilities for more efficient and accurate real-time object detection and tracking, enabling drones to perform sophisticated tasks and provide valuable insights in various domains.

- *Quantum-Based Video Analytics [29]: Quantum algorithms can enhance video analytics capabilities, allowing drones to perform complex tasks such as scene understanding, anomaly detection, and behavioral analysis in real-time.*

Quantum-based video analytics is an emerging field that explores the application of quantum computing algorithms to enhance video analytics capabilities. By leveraging the unique properties of quantum computing, such as quantum parallelism and superposition, quantum algorithms have the

potential to enable drones to perform complex tasks in real-time, such as scene understanding, anomaly detection, and behavioral analysis. Video analytics involves extracting meaningful information from video data, enabling automated interpretation and analysis of visual content. In the context of drones, video analytics can provide valuable insights for a wide range of applications, including surveillance, security, traffic monitoring, and environmental monitoring. Quantum algorithms can enhance video analytics by offering more efficient and powerful methods for processing and analyzing large volumes of video data. These algorithms can perform simultaneous computations on multiple possibilities, enabling faster and more comprehensive analysis of video frames and sequences. For instance, quantum algorithms can be used to perform scene understanding tasks, where the algorithms extract semantic information from video frames, such as object recognition, scene classification, and activity recognition. By leveraging quantum parallelism, these algorithms can explore different combinations of features and patterns, enabling more accurate and robust scene understanding capabilities.

Anomaly detection is another important application of quantum-based video analytics. Drones equipped with quantum algorithms can analyze video streams in real-time to detect abnormal or suspicious events, such as unauthorized access, unusual behavior, or potential security threats. Quantum algorithms can enable more effective anomaly detection by efficiently processing and analyzing complex patterns and relationships in video data. Behavioral analysis is yet another area where quantum-based video analytics can make a significant impact. By leveraging quantum algorithms, drones can analyze the behavior of individuals or objects within video streams, identifying patterns, trends, and deviations from expected behavior. This capability is valuable for applications such as crowd monitoring, traffic analysis, and wildlife tracking. However, it's important to note that quantum-based video analytics is still an emerging field, and practical implementations are yet to be fully realized. Quantum computers with sufficient power and stability for complex video analytics tasks are still in development. Additionally, quantum algorithms need further research, optimization, and testing to evaluate their effectiveness in real-world scenarios. Nonetheless, the potential of quantum-based video analytics offers exciting prospects for drones to perform advanced tasks in real-time. As quantum computing technology continues to advance, it may unlock new possibilities for more efficient and accurate video analytics capabilities, enabling drones to provide valuable insights and automated analysis in various domains.

C. Video Transmission and Communication

➤ *Quantum-Enabled Video Streaming Protocols [17]: Quantum computing can contribute to the development of efficient video streaming protocols that ensure low latency, high bandwidth utilization, and reliable transmission of drone video feeds.*

Quantum-enabled video streaming protocols have the potential to revolutionize the efficiency and reliability of video transmission from drones. By harnessing the power of

quantum computing, these protocols aim to address the challenges of low latency, high bandwidth utilization, and reliable data transmission. Although practical implementations are still in the early stages, the concept holds promise for future advancements in drone video streaming technology. The key features and benefits of quantum-enabled video streaming protocols can be summarized as follows. The first benefit is Low Latency. Quantum computing algorithms can optimize the encoding, decoding, and transmission processes, reducing the delay between video capture and playback. This reduced latency enables real-time streaming and enhances the responsiveness of drone video feeds, making them suitable for time-sensitive applications such as surveillance, emergency response, and remote inspections. The second benefit is High Bandwidth Utilization: Quantum-enabled protocols can leverage advanced compression techniques to efficiently encode and transmit video data, maximizing the utilization of available network bandwidth. By reducing the amount of data required for streaming, these protocols can minimize network congestion and ensure smoother video playback, even in bandwidth-constrained environments.

The third benefit is Reliable Transmission. Quantum computing algorithms can improve error correction and fault tolerance mechanisms within the streaming protocols, enhancing the reliability of data transmission. This increased resilience helps overcome challenges such as packet loss, signal interference, and network disruptions, ensuring the continuous and uninterrupted delivery of video feeds from drones. The fourth benefit is Security Enhancements. Quantum computing techniques can also contribute to the development of robust encryption and authentication mechanisms for securing drone video streams. Quantum cryptography algorithms can provide stronger protection against eavesdropping, data tampering, and unauthorized access, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive video content. While the practical implementation of quantum-enabled video streaming protocols in the drone industry is still a subject of ongoing research and development, the potential benefits are significant. As quantum computing technology advances and becomes more accessible, it is expected to shape the future of drone video streaming, enabling efficient, low-latency, and reliable transmission of high-quality video feeds.

➤ *Quantum-Based Network Optimization [5]: Quantum algorithms can optimize network resources, routing, and bandwidth allocation to enhance the quality of video streaming from drones, ensuring smooth and uninterrupted transmission.*

Quantum-based network optimization is an area of research that explores the application of quantum computing algorithms to improve the performance and efficiency of networks involved in video streaming from drones. By leveraging the capabilities of quantum computing, these algorithms aim to optimize network resources, routing, and bandwidth allocation, ultimately enhancing the quality and reliability of video transmission. Quantum algorithms can address various network optimization challenges. The first challenge is in Resource Allocation. Quantum algorithms can

optimize the allocation of network resources, such as bandwidth, to ensure efficient utilization and prioritization for video streaming from drones. By considering multiple possibilities simultaneously, quantum algorithms can explore different resource allocation strategies and identify the most effective approach to optimize video transmission. The second challenge is in Routing Optimization. Quantum algorithms can enhance routing algorithms by finding the most efficient paths for video data to be transmitted from drones to the receiving end. These algorithms can consider factors such as network congestion, latency, and available bandwidth to dynamically adapt the routing paths and minimize delays and packet loss during video streaming.

The third challenge is in Bandwidth Optimization. Quantum algorithms can optimize the allocation of available bandwidth among multiple streams, ensuring fair and efficient distribution to maintain the quality of video streaming. By dynamically adjusting the bandwidth allocation based on real-time network conditions, quantum-based optimization can mitigate bottlenecks and congestion, resulting in smoother and uninterrupted video playback. The fourth challenge is with Quality of Service (QoS) Optimization. Quantum algorithms can optimize the QoS parameters for video streaming, including factors like packet loss, delay, and jitter. By considering the quantum properties of superposition and entanglement, these algorithms can identify optimal configurations and settings that minimize QoS degradation and ensure a high-quality video streaming experience from drones. It's important to note that quantum-based network optimization is still an emerging field, and practical implementations are yet to be fully realized. Quantum computers with sufficient power and stability for complex network optimization tasks are still under development. Additionally, quantum algorithms need further research, refinement, and testing to evaluate their effectiveness and scalability in real-world scenarios. Nevertheless, the potential of quantum-based network optimization offers promising prospects for improving the quality and reliability of video streaming from drones. As quantum computing technology continues to advance, it may unlock new possibilities for more efficient network resource allocation, routing optimization, and bandwidth management, ultimately enhancing the overall video streaming experience from drones.

D. Security and Encryption

➤ *Quantum-Based Video Encryption [1]: Quantum cryptography techniques can provide secure video encryption, protecting the privacy and integrity of drone video streams from potential eavesdropping or tampering.*

Quantum-based video encryption leverages the principles of quantum cryptography to provide enhanced security for drone video streams. By utilizing the unique properties of quantum mechanics, such as quantum key distribution (QKD), quantum encryption algorithms can protect the privacy and integrity of video data, guarding against potential eavesdropping or tampering. The key aspects and benefits of quantum-based video encryption are as follows. The first is Quantum Key Distribution (QKD). QKD is a secure key distribution method that relies on the principles

of quantum mechanics to exchange encryption keys between the sender (drone) and the receiver (end-user). QKD ensures that any attempt to intercept the keys is detectable, thus providing a high level of security. Quantum encryption algorithms can utilize QKD to establish shared secret keys between the drone and the recipient, enabling secure communication and encryption of the video stream. The second is Unconditional Security. Quantum-based video encryption provides a higher level of security compared to classical encryption methods. It is based on the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics, which offer strong protection against computational attacks, including those performed by future quantum computers. The inherent properties of quantum mechanics, such as the no-cloning theorem and the observer effect, make it extremely difficult for an adversary to intercept or tamper with the encrypted video data without being detected.

The third is Data Privacy. Quantum encryption ensures the privacy of drone video streams by protecting them from unauthorized access. Encryption algorithms convert the video data into an unintelligible form using cryptographic keys, making it virtually impossible for unauthorized individuals to decipher the content without the corresponding decryption keys. This ensures that only authorized recipients with the correct keys can access and view the video stream. The fourth is Integrity and Authentication. Quantum-based encryption algorithms can also provide integrity and authentication features, ensuring that the video stream remains unchanged and unaltered during transmission. By incorporating cryptographic techniques such as digital signatures and message authentication codes, the receiver can verify the authenticity and integrity of the video data, detecting any unauthorized modifications or tampering attempts. While quantum-based video encryption holds significant promise, it's important to note that practical implementations are still in the early stages of development. Quantum computers with sufficient power and stability for complex encryption tasks are still being researched and engineered. Additionally, quantum encryption algorithms require further refinement, testing, and standardization to ensure their effectiveness and compatibility with existing infrastructure. Nonetheless, the potential of quantum-based video encryption offers a new frontier for securing drone video streams. As quantum computing technology progresses, it may enable stronger and more resilient encryption techniques, safeguarding the privacy and integrity of drone video data in an increasingly interconnected and vulnerable digital landscape.

➤ *Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) [7]: Quantum algorithms can enable the secure exchange of encryption keys for video streaming, ensuring robust encryption and decryption processes between drones and receiving devices.*

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) is a secure key exchange method that utilizes the principles of quantum mechanics to establish a shared secret key between the sender (drone) and the recipient (receiving device) for encryption and decryption of video streams. By leveraging the properties of quantum mechanics, QKD offers a high level of security, protecting the encryption keys from potential eavesdropping

or tampering attempts. The key features and benefits of using quantum algorithms for secure key exchange in video streaming are as follows. The first is Quantum Uncertainty. Quantum algorithms exploit the inherent uncertainty and non-cloning properties of quantum mechanics. This means that any attempt to intercept or measure the quantum state of the transmitted keys will disturb the system, alerting the sender and recipient to the presence of an eavesdropper. This property ensures the confidentiality of the encryption keys and protects against potential attacks. The second is Key Verification. Quantum algorithms in QKD protocols provide mechanisms for verifying the integrity and authenticity of the exchanged encryption keys. The sender and recipient can perform tests to check if the keys have been compromised during transmission. If any discrepancies or irregularities are detected, the parties can abort the key exchange process and establish a new secure channel, ensuring the security of the video stream.

The third is Robust Security. QKD offers a high level of security by leveraging the laws of physics. Unlike classical encryption methods, which rely on computational complexity, QKD provides "unconditional security" based on fundamental principles of quantum mechanics. This makes it highly resistant to attacks by both classical and future quantum computers, providing long-term security for video streaming applications. The fourth is Forward Secrecy. Quantum algorithms in QKD enable forward secrecy, meaning that even if an adversary manages to compromise a portion of the encryption keys, it cannot decrypt past or future communications. Each quantum key used in QKD is typically used for a single session, and the keys are continuously updated to maintain the security of ongoing video streams. It's important to note that practical implementation of QKD for video streaming is still in the early stages, and there are technical challenges to overcome. Factors such as quantum hardware limitations, transmission distance, and integration with existing infrastructure need to be addressed to ensure scalability and compatibility with real-world applications. Nevertheless, the potential of quantum algorithms in QKD offers a promising approach for establishing secure encryption keys in video streaming scenarios. As quantum computing technology continues to advance, it may enable more robust and efficient implementations of QKD, enhancing the security and privacy of video streams transmitted from drones to receiving devices.

E. Quality of Service (QoS) Optimization

➤ *Quantum-Based QoS Monitoring [30]: Quantum computing algorithms can monitor and analyze various QoS metrics such as video resolution, frame rate, and latency in real-time, ensuring optimal video streaming performance.*

Quantum-based QoS (Quality of Service) monitoring involves the use of quantum computing algorithms to analyze and assess various metrics related to video streaming performance in real-time. By leveraging the computational power of quantum computers, these algorithms can monitor and optimize factors such as video resolution, frame rate, latency, and other QoS parameters to ensure optimal video

streaming performance from drones. The key aspects and benefits of quantum-based QoS monitoring in video streaming are as follows: (1) Real-Time Analysis - Quantum algorithms can process and analyze large volumes of streaming data in real-time, enabling instant feedback and insights into the quality of the video stream. This real-time analysis allows for immediate adjustments and optimizations to be made, ensuring a consistent and optimal viewing experience for end-users. (2) Video Resolution Optimization - Quantum-based QoS monitoring algorithms can assess the available network bandwidth and dynamically adjust the video resolution based on the device capabilities and network conditions. By continuously monitoring and optimizing the video resolution, these algorithms ensure that the highest possible quality is maintained while avoiding excessive buffering or degradation in the stream. (3) Frame Rate Management - Quantum algorithms can monitor the frame rate of the video stream and optimize it based on the network conditions and device capabilities. By dynamically adjusting the frame rate, the algorithms can ensure smooth and seamless playback, minimizing any stuttering or frame drops that may affect the viewing experience. (4) Latency Control - Quantum-based QoS monitoring algorithms can track the latency of the video stream, measuring the delay between the time the video is captured by the drone and the time it is received and displayed on the receiving device. By monitoring and minimizing latency, these algorithms can provide a more responsive and real-time viewing experience, particularly in applications that require immediate feedback, such as live streaming or remote drone operations. (5) Adaptive Optimization - Quantum algorithms can adaptively optimize various QoS parameters based on the dynamic network conditions and viewer requirements. By continuously monitoring and analyzing the streaming data, these algorithms can make real-time adjustments to ensure the best possible video quality and performance, adapting to changing network conditions and user preferences. While the practical implementation of quantum-based QoS monitoring is still in its early stages, the potential benefits it offers for optimizing video streaming performance from drones are significant. As quantum computing technology advances and becomes more accessible, it may enable more efficient and accurate QoS monitoring algorithms, leading to enhanced video streaming experiences with optimal quality, resolution, frame rates, and reduced latency.

➤ *Quantum-Based QoS Control [19]: Quantum algorithms can dynamically adjust video streaming parameters based on changing network conditions, ensuring consistent and high-quality video delivery from drones.*

Quantum-based QoS (Quality of Service) control involves the utilization of quantum algorithms to dynamically adjust video streaming parameters based on changing network conditions. By leveraging the computational capabilities of quantum computers, these algorithms can optimize and maintain consistent, high-quality video delivery from drones, ensuring an optimal viewing experience for end-users. The key aspects and benefits of quantum-based QoS control in video streaming are as follows: (1) Adaptive Parameter Optimization - Quantum algorithms can continuously monitor and analyze network conditions, such as available bandwidth,

congestion levels, and packet loss rates. Based on this real-time analysis, the algorithms can dynamically adjust video streaming parameters, including bitrate, resolution, and compression settings, to ensure optimal delivery. By adaptively optimizing these parameters, quantum-based QoS control can maintain a high-quality video stream that is tailored to the current network conditions. (2) Bandwidth Allocation - Quantum algorithms can optimize the allocation of available bandwidth among multiple video streams from drones. By dynamically adjusting the bandwidth allocation based on the network's capacity and demand, these algorithms can prevent congestion and ensure that each video stream receives sufficient bandwidth for smooth playback. This optimization helps to maintain consistent video quality and minimize buffering or interruptions. (3) Latency Management - Quantum-based QoS control algorithms can optimize latency in video streaming from drones by minimizing transmission delays and optimizing the encoding and decoding processes. By reducing latency, the algorithms enable real-time or near-real-time video delivery, which is particularly crucial in applications such as live streaming or remote drone operations where low latency is essential for timely decision-making or interactive experiences. (4) Quality Preservation - Quantum algorithms can ensure the preservation of video quality during streaming by dynamically adjusting video parameters to match the available network resources. For example, in situations where the network capacity is limited, the algorithms can adaptively reduce the video resolution or adjust the compression level to maintain an acceptable level of video quality without sacrificing overall performance. (5) Robustness and Scalability - Quantum-based QoS control algorithms offer the potential for robust and scalable optimization solutions. Quantum computing's inherent parallelism and computational power enable efficient analysis of large amounts of streaming data, making it suitable for managing complex video streaming scenarios with multiple drones and a large number of viewers. While practical implementations of quantum-based QoS control in video streaming are still emerging, ongoing research and development in quantum computing hold promise for advancing these capabilities. As quantum technologies continue to mature, they may provide more efficient and scalable algorithms for real-time QoS control, leading to enhanced video delivery and improved user experiences in drone-based streaming applications.

It's important to note that quantum computing is still an evolving field, and practical implementations of quantum computing in drone video streaming are currently limited. However, ongoing research and advancements may lead to innovative solutions that leverage the power of quantum computing to enhance video streaming capabilities for drones in the future.

V. DISCUSSION

The taxonomy outlining potential use cases of quantum computing in drone video streaming technology can be beneficial in several ways. The first way is in Innovation and Performance Enhancement. Quantum computing algorithms have the potential to significantly enhance video compression,

image processing, and analytics tasks involved in drone video streaming. By leveraging quantum capabilities, such as improved optimization and processing power, drones can achieve higher video quality, reduced data sizes, and real-time advanced analytics. This innovation can lead to better situational awareness, more efficient data transmission, and improved decision-making during drone operations. The second way is in Bandwidth Optimization. Video streaming from drones can be bandwidth-intensive, especially when transmitting high-resolution or high-frame-rate video. Quantum-based video compression and network optimization techniques can help reduce the bandwidth requirements while maintaining or even improving the quality of the video stream. This can enable smoother and more reliable video transmission, even in environments with limited network resources.

The third way is with Real-Time Analytics and Object Tracking. Quantum computing algorithms applied to real-time video analytics, object detection, and tracking can enhance the capabilities of drones. This can enable automated scene understanding, anomaly detection, and behavioral analysis, allowing drones to perform complex tasks in real-time. It opens up possibilities for applications like surveillance, search and rescue, and industrial inspections, where drones can identify objects of interest or monitor specific activities during the video streaming. The fourth way is with Secure Video Transmission. Security is a critical concern when transmitting drone video streams, especially in sensitive applications like defense or critical infrastructure monitoring. Quantum-based encryption techniques and quantum key distribution (QKD) can provide robust security measures, protecting the privacy and integrity of the video feed. This ensures that the transmitted video data remains confidential and tamper-proof, even against potential eavesdropping or hacking attempts. The fifth way is in Quality of Service Optimization. Quantum-based QoS monitoring and control can improve the performance and user experience of drone video streaming. By analyzing real-time QoS metrics, such as resolution, frame rate, and latency, quantum computing algorithms can dynamically adjust video streaming parameters to maintain optimal performance. This leads to consistent and high-quality video delivery, reducing disruptions and improving the overall video streaming experience.

In general, the taxonomy helps identify potential applications of quantum computing in drone video streaming, addressing challenges related to video compression, analytics, transmission, security, and QoS optimization. These advancements can bring significant improvements to the quality, efficiency, and capabilities of drone video streaming technology, enabling new possibilities and enhancing the effectiveness of drone operations across various domains.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the taxonomy outlining the potential use cases of quantum computing in drone video streaming technology highlights the transformative possibilities that quantum computing can bring to the field. By leveraging quantum algorithms and techniques, drones can benefit from

enhanced video compression, real-time analytics, optimized transmission, secure encryption, and improved quality of service. The integration of quantum-based video compression enables more efficient encoding, reducing bandwidth requirements while maintaining high-quality video streams. Real-time video analytics powered by quantum algorithms allow drones to perform advanced tasks such as object detection, tracking, and scene understanding, enhancing situational awareness and decision-making capabilities. Quantum-enabled video streaming protocols optimize network resources, ensuring low latency, high bandwidth utilization, and reliable transmission of video feeds. Quantum-based encryption techniques and quantum key distribution offer robust security measures, safeguarding the privacy and integrity of drone video streams. Additionally, quantum-based quality of service monitoring and control dynamically adapt video streaming parameters to changing network conditions, ensuring consistent and high-quality video delivery. While these applications showcase the potential benefits, it's important to note that quantum computing is still an evolving field, and its practical implementation in drone video streaming technology is currently limited. Continued research and development are necessary to fully exploit the capabilities of quantum computing and overcome challenges such as hardware limitations, algorithmic development, and integration complexities. Nevertheless, the taxonomy provides a roadmap for the future, highlighting the areas where quantum computing can bring significant improvements to drone video streaming. With further advancements and innovations, quantum computing has the potential to revolutionize drone operations, enabling more efficient, secure, and advanced video streaming capabilities.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abd El-Latif, A.A., Abd-El-Atty, B., Mazurczyk, W., Fung, C. and Venegas-Andraca, S.E., 2020. Secure data encryption based on quantum walks for 5G Internet of Things scenario. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 17(1), pp.118-131.
- [2]. Agrawal, A., Abraham, S.J., Burger, B., Christine, C., Fraser, L., Hoeksema, J.M., Hwang, S., Travnik, E., Kumar, S., Scheirer, W. and Cleland-Huang, J., 2020, April. The next generation of human-drone partnerships: Co-designing an emergency response system. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1-13).
- [3]. Alarifi, A., Sankar, S., Altameem, T., Jithin, K.C., Amoon, M. and El-Shafai, W., 2020. A novel hybrid cryptosystem for secure streaming of high efficiency H. 265 compressed videos in IoT multimedia applications. *IEEE Access*, 8, pp.128548-128573.
- [4]. Bera, B., Das, A.K., Garg, S., Piran, M.J. and Hossain, M.S., 2021. Access control protocol for battlefield surveillance in drone-assisted IoT environment. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9(4), pp.2708-2721.
- [5]. Bhatia, M. and Sood, S.K., 2020. Quantum computing-inspired network optimization for IoT applications. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(6), pp.5590-5598.
- [6]. Budiyanto, S. and Gunawan, D., 2023. Comparative Analysis of VPN Protocols at Layer 2 Focusing on Voice over Internet Protocol. *IEEE Access*.
- [7]. Cao, Y., Zhao, Y., Wang, Q., Zhang, J., Ng, S.X. and Hanzo, L., 2022. The evolution of quantum key distribution networks: On the road to the qinternet. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 24(2), pp.839-894.
- [8]. Funasaka, J., 2020, November. Evaluation on Progressive Download Methods Based on Timer-Driven Requesting Schemes on Multiple Paths with Shared Links. In *2020 Eighth International Symposium on Computing and Networking Workshops (CANDARW)* (pp. 14-20). IEEE.
- [9]. Gyongyosi, L. and Imre, S., 2019. A survey on quantum computing technology. *Computer Science Review*, 31, pp.51-71.
- [10]. Halder, S. and Afsari, K., 2023. Robots in inspection and monitoring of buildings and infrastructure: A systematic review. *Applied Sciences*, 13(4), p.2304.
- [11]. Haque, M.E., Paul, M., Ulhaq, A. and Debnath, T., 2023. Advanced quantum image representation and compression using a DCT-EFRQI approach. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), p.4129.
- [12]. Jiang, N., Dong, X., Hu, H., Ji, Z. and Zhang, W., 2019. Quantum image encryption based on Henon mapping. *International Journal of Theoretical Physics*, 58, pp.979-991.
- [13]. Khan, K. and Goodridge, W., 2018. Future DASH applications: A survey. *International Journal of Advanced Networking and Applications*, 10(2), pp.3758-3764.
- [14]. Khan, K. and Goodridge, W., 2018. QoE in DASH. *International Journal of Advanced Networking and Applications*, 9(4), pp.3515-3522.
- [15]. Khan, K. and Goodridge, W., 2020. Reinforcement Learning in DASH. *International Journal of Advanced Networking and Applications*, 11(5), pp.4386-4392.
- [16]. KHAN, K. and GOODRIDGE, W., 2022. Ultra-HD Video Streaming in 5G Fixed Wireless Access Bottlenecks.
- [17]. Kumar, A., Suleymanzade, A., Stone, M., Taneja, L., Anferov, A., Schuster, D.I. and Simon, J., 2023. Quantum-enabled millimetre wave to optical transduction using neutral atoms. *Nature*, 615(7953), pp.614-619.
- [18]. Li, Z., Duanmu, Z., Liu, W. and Wang, Z., 2019. AVC, HEVC, VP9, AVS2 OR AV1?—A comparative study of state-of-the-art video encoders on 4K videos. In *Image Analysis and Recognition: 16th International Conference, ICIAR 2019, Waterloo, ON, Canada, August 27–29, 2019, Proceedings, Part I 16* (pp. 162-173). Springer International Publishing.
- [19]. Liu, Y., Li, C., Zhang, Y., Xu, M., Xiao, J. and Zhou, J., 2022. HPCP-QCWOA: High performance clustering protocol based on quantum clone whale optimization algorithm in integrated energy system. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 135, pp.315-332.
- [20]. Loke, M., JosephNg, P.S., Shibghatullah, A.S. and Eaw, H.C., 2020, July. Jomdrone: Data mining financial sense in the property agency. In *2020 IEEE Symposium*

- on Industrial Electronics & Applications (ISIEA) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [21]. Mademlis, I., Mygdalis, V., Nikolaidis, N., Montagnuolo, M., Negro, F., Messina, A. and Pitas, I., 2019. High-level multiple-UAV cinematography tools for covering outdoor events. *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, 65(3), pp.627-635.
- [22]. McRae, J.N., Gay, C.J., Nielsen, B.M. and Hunt, A.P., 2019. Using an unmanned aircraft system (drone) to conduct a complex high altitude search and rescue operation: a case study. *Wilderness & environmental medicine*, 30(3), pp.287-290.
- [23]. Mystakidis, S., Fragkaki, M. and Filippousis, G., 2021. Ready teacher one: Virtual and augmented reality online professional development for K-12 school teachers. *Computers*, 10(10), p.134.
- [24]. Rahe, V., Buschow, C. and Schlütz, D., 2021. How users approach novel media products: Brand perception of Netflix and Amazon Prime video as signposts within the German subscription-based video-on-demand market. *Journal of Media Business Studies*, 18(1), pp.45-58.
- [25]. Raj, T., Hanim Hashim, F., Baseri Huddin, A., Ibrahim, M.F. and Hussain, A., 2020. A survey on LiDAR scanning mechanisms. *Electronics*, 9(5), p.741.
- [26]. Shahmoradi, J., Talebi, E., Roghanchi, P. and Hassanalian, M., 2020. A comprehensive review of applications of drone technology in the mining industry. *Drones*, 4(3), p.34.
- [27]. Shreyas, E. and Sheth, M.H., 2021, August. 3D Object Detection and Tracking Methods using Deep Learning for Computer Vision Applications. In *2021 International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information, Communication & Technology (RTEICT)* (pp. 735-738). IEEE.
- [28]. Suryono, R.R., Purwandari, B. and Budi, I., 2019. Peer to peer (P2P) lending problems and potential solutions: A systematic literature review. *Procedia Computer Science*, 161, pp.204-214.
- [29]. Tziridis, K., Kalampokas, T. and Papakostas, G.A., 2023. Quantum Image Analysis–Status and Perspectives. *Intelligent Image and Video Analytics*, 6(6.3), p.173.
- [30]. Veni, T., 2022. Quantum-Based Resource Management Approaches in Fog Computing Environments: A Comprehensive Review. *Mobile Computing and Sustainable Informatics: Proceedings of ICMCSI 2022*, pp.743-752.
- [31]. Vujičić, M.D., Kennell, J., Stankov, U., Gretzel, U., Vasiljević, Đ.A. and Morrison, A.M., 2022. Keeping up with the drones! Techno-social dimensions of tourist drone videography. *Technology in Society*, 68, p.101838.
- [32]. Zhang, M. and Li, X., 2020. Drone-enabled Internet-of-Things relay for environmental monitoring in remote areas without public networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(8), pp.7648-7662.